

The Making of Data Liquidity

Embeddings in a navigable *milieu* and the hermeneutics of latent space

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Abstract

According to the discourses accompanying the fourth paradigm, one of the conditions for its realisation would be the fluidity of the data — “data liquidity” — on which it is based. The metaphor of the “data lake”, for example — used from 2011 onwards to describe a storage format for data of very diverse natures and formats, structured or unstructured, often without knowing what use they will be put to — has subsequently emancipated itself from its technical context to embody the hydraulic ideal of perpetual, frictionless recombination. In short, it is the fluidity of supposedly unstructured masses of data that would enable practices to be “un-siloed” and new knowledge to be produced. This would open up the new analytical possibilities of the fourth paradigm: the changing nature of results when processing large quantities of data, the equivalence of empirical materials of heterogeneous natures in a common space, the automation of these processes in their embodiment by self-learning machines. Yet there is nothing spontaneous or natural about the liquidity of data, which paradoxically needs to be structured to guarantee seamless, frictionless navigation. This contribution aims to shed light on *the making of data liquidity* by examining the operational chain of the *word2vec* embedding algorithm in digital humanities.

Résumé

Selon les discours d'escorte du quatrième paradigme, l'une des conditions de sa réalisation serait la fluidité des données — “*data liquidity*” — sur lesquelles il se fonde. La métaphore du “lac de données”, par exemple, — utilisée à partir de 2011 pour décrire un format de stockage de données de natures et formats très divers, structurées ou non, souvent sans savoir quel en sera l'usage — s'est par la suite émancipée de son contexte technique pour incarner l'idéal hydraulique de la recombinaison perpétuelle et sans friction. En somme, c'est la fluidité de masses informes de données supposées non structurées qui permettrait le “désilotage” des pratiques et la production de savoirs nouveaux. Avec elle s'ouvriraient les possibilités d'analyse nouvelles du quatrième paradigme : le changement de nature des résultats dans le traitement de grandes quantités de données, la mise en équivalence de matériaux empiriques de natures hétérogènes dans un espace commun, l'automatisation de ces procédés dans leur incarnation par des machines auto-apprenantes. Pourtant, rien de spontané ou de naturel dans la liquidité des données qui, paradoxalement,

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nécessitent d'être structurées afin de garantir une navigation “*seamless*” et sans friction. Cette contribution se propose de mettre au jour *la fabrique de la liquidité des données* en se penchant sur la chaîne opératoire de l'algorithme de plongement *word2vec* en humanités numériques.

Keywords

data, liquid, embedding, digital humanities, hermeneutics

Mots-clés

données, liquide, plongement, humanités numériques, herméneutique

Introduction

A deluge — it is in the guise of an apocalyptic cataclysm that the advent of the “fourth paradigm” in science presents itself. The famous “Scientific Revolution” of the modern era, fiercely debated, pales in comparison to the prophecy of a hydraulic cataclysm of biblical proportions that would engulf previous paradigms, render “the scientific method obsolete” (Anderson, 2008), and wipe the slate clean of the history of science. The irruption of “data” in formless, liquid masses would thus represent a peril for science, but a peril fraught with opportunity — a promise that would, *a priori*, justify the (creative) destruction of the scientific edifice sedimented over the centuries.

Grounded in a reductionist epistemology that defines *science* as “data-intensive computing” (Hey *et al.* , 2009, p. xi), the fourth paradigm thus claims to inaugurate the primacy of data in the production of knowledge — and to firmly anchor perfect inductivism in this primacy, thanks to supposedly neutral analytical methods. Paradoxically, this renews the promises of a supposed scientific revolution based on four major principles: radical empiricism, radical inductivism, exhaustive data, and the neutrality of the analytical framework. Thus produced, knowledge itself “becomes ‘liquid’ and its flow, from research to practice, is frictionless *and* immediate” (Hey *et al.* , 2009, p. 61). From data to knowledge, the liquid metaphor infuses the entire scientific “*workflow*” and this “flow” guarantees immediate knowledge, that is to say both “instantaneous” (Hey *et al.* , 2009, p. 59) and unmediated, therefore objective, in adherence to reality.

However, in order to channel this deluge of data and make it productive, proponents of the fourth paradigm insist on the need to develop and deploy a large-scale infrastructure for data capture, curation , analysis, and visualisation (Hey *et al.* , 2009, p. 17). The diluvian chaos would thus only become creative destruction at the cost of a process of infrastructuralisation, a paradoxical attempt to organise instability². A condition of possibility for the fourth paradigm, what the infrastructure must support is not only the influx of data — through, for example, *pipelines* — but also the flow of knowledge subjects within a truly “seamlessly *navigable and interoperable*” environment (Hey *et al.* , 2009, p. 185). Like surfing the Web, the “end of theory” (Anderson, 2008) would therefore be the advent of a new order of knowledge, a fluid order that would know neither partition nor silo, a perfectly continuous and continuously navigable medium where data flows and subjects of knowledge would cruise immediately and without friction³.

The (asymptotic) creation of a fluid continuum, however, does not occur through simple passive dissolution — *i.e.*, by merely collecting and allowing unstructured, formless masses to bathe — but rather

² On infrastructure and the “invisible work of data”, see Denis (2018).

³ More generally, these metaphors are part of a contemporary fluid imaginary, that of a reality without structure (Bauman, 2006), in a permanent movement of flow and reflux of information and subjects (Castells, 1998).

results from various active operations through paradoxically structuring and crystallising technical processes⁴. This is what we propose to demonstrate through the semiotic-technical analysis of a key machine learning process⁵: the *embedding*, that is, the generation of continuous spaces of data representation. Indeed, embedding, by generating a unique and shared latent space, places each *datum* within a neighborhood, a *continuum* whose nature and epistemic scope are open to question. This remediation, possible for any input data, became, with the advent of deep learning models around 2012, the canonical operation for creating the continuum within the framework of the fourth paradigm.

In the field of metaphor analysis, the semantic field of hydraulics has often been inventoried and sometimes discussed, whether to designate digital technology in general (Bernardot, 2018) or data in particular (Puschmann and Burgess, 2014; Stark and Hoffmann, 2019; Nolin, 2020). Here oil, there water, elsewhere an indistinct liquid forming lakes⁶, oceans, and floods — data in its metaphorical *fluidity* has primarily been the subject of commentary regarding its economic significance as “resources.” However, the link between these metaphors and the resulting order of knowledge is rarely discussed, particularly in relation to the socio-technical systems that are supposed to guarantee this fluidity. Indeed, in the field of media archaeology and practices, while many data ordering processes — in particular their vectorisation — have been the subject of both technical and philosophical commentary (Mackenzie, 2017; Offert, 2020; Dobson, 2022), these have mainly focused on the upstream analytical operation of transforming a corpus into a bag of words (e.g., Gavin, 2020), as well as on the downstream operation of their visualisation and interpretation, and more rarely on the synthetic operation of generating a continuous vector space enabling navigation.

At the intersection of these two corpora, this contribution proposes a study of the link between the fluid rhetoric of data and the creation of continuous spaces for data manipulation and the navigation of knowledge subjects. This fundamentally epistemological problem of text analysis using natural language processing algorithms has taken the form of a debate on the place of hermeneutics in the digitally equipped humanities and social sciences (HSS) — particularly the digital humanities. However, rather than an exception, the HSS should be considered an edge case that highlights the tensions essential to any data analysis. Thus, we hope to contribute to the development of a “digital hermeneutics” (Fickers *et al.* ,

⁴ This problem of continuum synthesis evokes precedents in the history of science and technology. Leibniz's infinitesimal calculus, for example, allows us to reconstruct, asymptotically, the continuity of a curve or an area through the integration — a continuous sum — of infinitesimal discrete elements. Or, in a technical extension of this problem, pioneered by Shannon's work in signal processing, the reconstruction of a sound signal from its sampling.

⁵ Other processes besides the one chosen fall under this same logic of constructing the liquid continuum by structuring data: the alignment of controlled vocabularies or ontologies, in particular with the aim of converging towards a single vocabulary or ontology, as well as diffusion models that produce images from noise.

⁶ The use of the term “data lake” remains strongly rooted in its original infrastructural context: a reservoir of large quantities of data, most often organised around a knowledge graph. While this term is closer to the spirit of the semantic web than to deep learning, the fluid metaphor nonetheless resonates with us and points to the same fantasy of fluidity. In our view, it reflects a commonality with what we will develop: the conversion of large datasets into a homogeneous format, which opens up a system of limitless comparison, combination, and inference.

2022) that allows for a critique of the fourth paradigm even in the natural sciences and computer science⁷.

This contribution therefore aims to question the liquid metaphor at the roots of the fourth paradigm by examining the creation of data liquidity — in particular through the use of the *word2vec* algorithm to process *text*, which we deem to be the original, canonical *medium* of the fourth paradigm and of knowledge since the scientific revolution. By combining media-theoretical analysis (Geoghegan, 2023), philosophy of technology (Bachimont, 2021), and archaeology of data practices (McKenzie, 2017), we propose to examine this shift from the static discreteness of data to the dynamic continuum of fluidity by detailing the “operational chain” of the *word2vec* digital embedding process. First, this contribution will offer a close reading of the text and seminal algorithm of *word2vec* (Mikolov *et al.*, 2013), highlighting the historical and scientific context of the production of this continuum-making device, as well as the epistemological material operations that the method performs on its input data in order to generate a continuous space for navigation. We will then focus on the navigation methods that the subject of knowledge, mediated by algorithms and visualisation tools, can deploy within this space in order to produce knowledge — as well as beyond it, toward other spaces that form a network. Finally, in light of these analyses, we will return to the place occupied by fluid continuity within the fourth paradigm and the consequent need to consider it, rather than as a deluge or revolution, in a relationship of sedimentation with disciplinary paradigms and practices that historically precede and outlive it.

1. The synthesis of a continuously navigable space

While the *word2vec* text vectorisation algorithm is not the first of its kind (subsection 1) and has since been superseded by the introduction of large language models (LLMs), it nevertheless offers a perfect vantage point for the embedding method, *i.e.*, the synthesis of a continuous space (latent space) from discrete data (bag of words) through vectorisation (subsection 2)⁸. Widely used for over a decade in the digital humanities, it inaugurates a textual representation space that allows for vector algebraic computation on minimal entities of meaning. It is this computation that makes it possible to reproduce meaning by displacement, within a continuous medium, of a subject mediated by clustering, dimensionality reduction, or visualisation algorithms (subsection 3). From text to bag of words to latent space, we attempt to uncover the operational chain of *word2vec* and the changes undergone by the data to produce a continuously navigable environment, itself inscribed in a network of other representations (subsection 4).

1.1. From cybernetics to *computational humanities*

This quest for a mathematical space in which to place numerical representations of units of meaning (words, documents, images) is not new and has marked the early decades of cybernetics in all its fields of application. The concept of “vector space” began to be used to represent text as early as the 1970s, notably by Gerard Salton (Dubin, 2004). While this space addressed the limited problem of information

⁷ “Exploration of the hermeneutic potential of computation is a challenge that digital humanities could pose, to itself and to computer science on behalf of the humanities. This need not imply transforming the nature of computation, but it must involve remediating the nature of hermeneutics through computational logic and design informed strongly by a dialog with humanities. It is apparent that scientific methods deriving from the humanities would be more appropriate than scientism for artificial intelligence and computer science when interacting with the humanities.”(van Zundert, 2016, pp. 344-5)

⁸ Our analysis therefore applies, *mutatis mutandis*, to other algorithmic solutions to the problem of the vector representation of the world, which in the era of *deep learning* and the hegemony of LLMs appears to us to be central.

retrieval typical of databases, Salton theorised several of its characteristics — such as cosine similarity and *one-of-n* binary vector encoding (*one-hot encoding*) — which would be adopted verbatim in the early computational humanities research of the late 1980s. In Salton's vector space, vectorisation is performed *a priori* and requires explicit encoding rules. A decade earlier, in the mid-1960s, researchers at Bell Labs, aware of this impending limitation, had developed the so-called “non-metric multidimensional scaling” (NMMDS) method. NMMDS was quickly adopted by psychologists and anthropologists interested in quantifying elusive concepts, particularly for its ability to transform a dataset into a space where conceptual proximity is visually expressed (Seaver, 2022).

Following this same logic of mathematising the humanities, postwar linguistics also turned to statistics as a descriptor. It is the context of a word that defines it and allows for the resolution of any semantic ambiguity⁹. Thus, according to the proponents of this “distributional semantics,” any formalisation of language involves the statistical study of co-occurrences (Harris, 1954). Summarising its principles, the British linguist John Firth declared, in a phrase since regularly repeated by proponents of vectorialisation: “You shall know a word by the company it keeps ” (1962, 11).

From the 1990s onward, distributional semantics, thanks to its ease of implementation, became central to early work in computational humanities¹⁰. Various approaches coexisted: bag-of-words, document-term matrices, and latent Dirichlet allocation for modelling the subjects or themes of a document corpus. At this stage, these vectors were rarely more than a reservoir of numbers, and while each dimension quantified membership in a group, the equivalence between position and concept promised by vector spaces was still lacking. This is what Bengio *et al.* (2003) proposed: a linguistically coherent spatial representation, achieved through a neural network that adapts its parameters according to the co-occurrences of words within a corpus.

1.2. *word2vec* : vectorise by embedding

Ten years later, *word2vec* improved upon this neural network machine learning (NNML) model of language and adopted its ambition of spatio-linguistic equivalence (Mikolov *et al.* , 2013). Less expensive to train, faster, capable of scaling with more data, and offering increased contextual sensitivity, *word2vec* quickly established itself as the new standard and propelled linguistic computation towards deep learning¹¹. In particular, its ability to significantly outperform classical language models in statistical comparison tests and its versatility — as demonstrated a few months later by an improved version integrating different languages — marked the triumph of vector embedding.

Beyond its technical and historical significance, if we take *word2vec* as an example, it is also because it is symptomatic of both the crucial challenge today of achieving ever-greater precision in understanding natural language, and the establishment of equivalence spaces between all data — all contexts, all *media*, all languages — through mathematical vectors — thus establishing data as a currency (Gingold, 2026).

⁹ Funded by the Rockefeller Foundation, a major patron of postwar cybernetics (Geoghegan, 2023), Warren Weaver advocated, first in a 1947 letter to Norbert Wiener and then in a 1949 memorandum on machine translation, the use of an “opaque mask” to determine the meaning of homonyms (Weaver 1949). What has since been called an “attention window” is now a component of every language model, including *word2vec* .

¹⁰ Pierre-Carl Langlais links the distributional semantics of Weaver and Firth to the work of Roman Jakobson, whose intellectual aura is said to have influenced Tomas Mikolov, the first author of the *word2vec* paper (Langlais, 2023).

¹¹ It should be noted, however, that *word2vec* does not, strictly speaking, offer a deep neural network architecture. On the contrary, its *shallowness* is what makes the model so easy to implement. Nevertheless, its training method and epistemic ambitions will remain those of deep learning.

Falling under what Chartier-Edwards *et al.* (2024) have called “vectorialism,” it is not insignificant that the research team behind *word2vec* came exclusively from Google. Yesterday as today, the central tools of cultural vectorisation come from private companies (Meta: LLaMa, Segment Anything; Google: *word2vec*, Transformers, BERT; OpenAI: GPT, Dall-E) before being taken up by public projects (Wark, 2015).

While the political implications of this concentration are beyond the scope of our contribution, it is worth noting that the interests of these companies — always on the lookout for an optimal solution from a performance standpoint, easily scalable, and therefore generic — are hardly compatible with fundamental research comprised of a plurality of practices and questions. This is particularly evident when one considers, for example, that the future applications of these new technologies are addressed in the article on *word2vec* only in a paragraph conceived *after the fact*, rather than stemming from the intrinsic motivation of a specific problem to be solved¹². Thus, text vectorisation appears as *the* conceptual solution, certainly improvable, but ready to be deployed to any textual problem — whether as diverse as “machine translation, information retrieval, and generic question-answering systems,” as well as “future applications yet to be invented” (Mikolov *et al.*, 2013, p. 5)¹³.

Vector space, spatio-conceptual equivalence, distributional semantics: these three concepts have permeated and remain today, after decades of application, the three building blocks upon which deep learning language models are based. Moreover, even though language was the initial testing ground — both due to technical limitations and the prior existence of a theoretical framework — it is clear that the vectorisation of cultural phenomena has, since the advent of deep learning, targeted an increasing number of domains. As Cardon *et al.* (2018) remind us: “according to Yann LeCun [one of the pioneers of deep learning], the ambition of the designers of connectionist machines is to put the world into a vector (*word2vec*)” (p. 206).

The *word2vec* operational chain¹⁴ incorporates several elements from the genealogy outlined above: first, a *corpus* of texts — *i.e.*, an organic and meaningful whole — is broken down into tokens, *i.e.*, smaller-scale units of meaning — in this case, words, themselves reduced to their lemmatised form and from which “*stopwords*” have been removed, that is, very common words with little meaning out of context, notably coordinating conjunctions, articles, deictics, etc. Thus, at the beginning of the chain, tokenization, lemmatization, and cleaning steps convert an (unspecified) corpus of texts from Google News into a set of six billion *tokens*. The resulting set may preserve the word order of the document; otherwise, it is a bag of *words*.

The next step in the operational chain is to assign a vector to each token. The major contribution of *word2vec* lies here in its two neural network architectures, *Continuous Bag of Words* (CBOW) and *Skip-gram*, both of which predict one or more words given one or more context words. By dragging a contextual window of variable width (between 2 and 20 words), it is possible to generate the billions of restricted linguistic contexts required by distributional semantics. Within these micro-sets of *n* words, the challenge for both architectures proposed by *word2vec* is to fill in the gaps: one missing word for CBOW, (*n* - 1)

¹² “We also expect that high-quality word vectors will become an important *building block for future NLP (natural language processing) applications.*” (Mikolov *et al.*, 2013, p. 8)

¹³ In fact, in 2019, Google moved its search engine from a keyword search mode, based on a network of referrals and mentions, to an interpretation of natural language by BERT, itself conceived as an extension of *word2vec*, capable of taking the context of a word into account, thus managing homonyms, and complete sentences (Devlin *et al.*, 2018).

¹⁴ We use here the definition of Robert Cresswell, derived from the work of André Leroi-Gourhan, namely a “series of operations which transform a raw material into a product, whether it is a consumer object or a finished tool” (n.a., 2019).

words to predict for Skip-gram. The relationship between what is known and what must be predicted is, however, inverse for the two tasks. On the one hand, CBOW consists of predicting a word given the words that follow and precede it. On the other, Skip-gram seeks to identify, for a single given word, the surrounding words. Neural training then consists of adjusting the parameters to optimise these predictions and progressively improve the conversion of a word into a vector with several hundred dimensions¹⁵. The imbalance between the two tasks justifies the advantages and disadvantages of the two architectures: quick to train but poor for rare words for CBOW, slow but more exhaustive for Skip-gram. However, while Skip-gram ultimately prevailed due to its superior performance, both architectures seem to achieve the authors' ambitions: at the end of the operational chain, a multidimensional Euclidean vector space is synthesised where each word is represented by a vector with a linguistically coherent neighbourhood. Already at this stage, a first hermeneutic reduction is performed: a word is transformed into a multidimensional vector with no explicit meaning, whose number can change without drastic performance loss, and which defies any mental representation. From this stage onward, to extend the fluid metaphor, meaning would seem to “slip through one's fingers.”

1.3. Producing meaning through displacement

One mathematical operation made possible by the synthesis of this space particularly captures the authors' attention: vector algebra. Even more than the static structure of points in space, it is the operation of displacement between two points (that is, the vector¹⁶) that is the true objective¹⁷. To every displacement in space, one can associate a conceptual linguistic operation. Thus, the now-famous example: $\text{vector}(\text{“King”}) - \text{vector}(\text{“Man”}) + \text{vector}(\text{“Woman”}) \approx \text{vector}(\text{“Queen”})$ (cf. Figure 1). It is by

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the latent space as mathematical embeddings and the possibility of vector algebra.

¹⁵ The original paper oscillates the dimensions of its vectors between 50 and 1000, a range that remained typical until the advent of large language models, now with tens of thousands of dimensions.

¹⁶ Note here the semantic difficulty: each word is associated, in a space, with a point — which is called a vector because of its large dimensions — but the movement between these word-points is also called a vector. From this confusion also arises the idea that the movement-vector can be associated with a word-vector.

¹⁷ What the authors call “linear regularities”: “We try to maximize the accuracy of these vector operations by developing new model architectures that preserve the linear regularities among words.” (2013, 2)

“moving through data” (Mackenzie, 2017, p. 69) that the subject can produce meaning: “Vectorized transformation of data is the moving substrate of machine learning as it expands, but it is largely taken for granted as given space or common sense ground.” (*Ibid.*, p. 67) It is against the backdrop of this operation that the vector space is evaluated. As the constructed space improves its coherence, any connection made based on mathematical operations (proximity, displacement, etc.) becomes a potential semantic discovery. This then opens the quest for an ever more precise vector space, requiring more resources, more training, more data, and more parameters.

It should be noted, however, that the passages that make vectorisation possible and operational are almost entirely ignored in the seminal article by Mikolov *et al.* (2013). The initial tokenisation steps are not explained, and no alternative seems possible. Similarly, the choice of training parameters (negative sampling, hierarchical *softmax*, dynamic attention window) is mentioned only in passing, even though they constitute the main reason for the success of *word2vec* according to the comparative study by Levy *et al.* (2015). These earlier and later steps in the operational chain — often overlooked in the accompanying discourse, which focuses on promoting reusable and therefore citable neural architectures — should nevertheless be central to any critique. In particular, the preparation operations flatten a large number of dimensions of the original document and reveal strong theoretical preconceptions.

These silences, in our view, reflect a spatial bias on the part of the authors. Conceptually, there is a *primacy of space*. This primacy is expressed in two ways. First, temporally, since it is something imposed on the data. Embedding is an operation applied to data, not a property. If points are embedded *in a continuous space*, it is because this space must first be mentally constructed, and the assumption that language is continuous must be taken as *a given* — despite the instruments of the social construction of language, whose conventions (e.g., grammar), devices (e.g., dictionary), and institutions (e.g., the French Academy) make it an assemblage of discrete entities.¹⁸ Before any algorithmic operation, that is, even before this space is tangible, we already perceive the fluid fantasy. It is the pre-existence of this fantasy that must be examined in relation to the disappearance of the theory.

Secondly, and perhaps more importantly, space is given an intention of its own. This is what the use of the term “*latent space*”, now hegemonic in digital humanities, reveals¹⁹. This spatio-conceptual equivalence, as we called it above, seems like a happy consequence: a conceptual coherence that, after remaining hidden in the topology, would manifest itself at a certain point, once learning is complete²⁰. That this space has meaning seems indeed to surprise its designers. The authors of *word2vec* state, for example: “Somewhat surprisingly, these questions can be answered by performing simple algebraic operations with the vector representation of words ” (Mikolov *et al.*, 2013, p. 5).

One reason for this surprise, beyond a certain techno-optimism, may stem from the very construction of the space: between the inevitable *manipulation* of data and the abstraction of a text corpus into digital

¹⁸ Furthermore, the continuity of the space into which language is projected raises the thorny problem of interpolating that space. In the case of images, it gives rise to new representations (hallucinations or otherwise) that form the basis of generative AI. What about textual interpolation?

¹⁹ It is worth noting that, for once in the global lexicon of machine learning, neighbouring linguistic domains all converge towards this definition of an emergence of meaning — since we speak of *espace latent*, *spazio latente*, *latentent Raum*, or *espacio latente*.

²⁰ Here we adapt the definition of *latent* given by the OED: “hidden, concealed; present or existing, but not manifest, exhibited, or developed”.

vectors, the emergence of a familiar structural form is striking²¹. Just as one must go through the discrete nature of tokens to create the continuum of latent space, theory is (supposedly) discarded, but the results of its recombination call for interpretation.

1.4. Inscribing embeddings into a network

This interpretative potential of vector space quickly attracted numerous research projects in the digital humanities where, following the attempts of computational humanities, embedding has taken a central place in the arsenal of methods deployed. But how, from such a complex vector object, does one produce knowledge? Indeed, as James E. Dobson reminds us, vector processing requires another algorithmic mediation: “Vector space representations of texts are not explicitly designed for human consumption but for algorithmic manipulation” (Dobson, 2020, p. 85). We could formulate the idea differently: a vector space can only be interpreted by weaving a set of internal and external relations within the space and navigating these relations. Here, the numerous digital humanities projects contribute to a taxonomy of operations.

The most frequently performed operations are those involving calculations *within* the embedding space itself — what Sybille Krämer would group under “intrinsic meaning” (Krämer, 2021, pp. 7–9). These computational operations intrinsic to the space can then be broken down into two types. On the one hand, analytical operations aimed at dividing the space into meaningful subsets (semantic fields or *topics*): for example, an analysis of the topology of the space itself by visualising saliences, through *clustering* using similarity calculations. On the other hand, navigation operations within the space that allow for the generation or classification of new points.

A second class of operations encompasses those that relate the embedding space to *other* spaces — “extrinsic meaning”, according to Krämer (2021, pp. 7–9). The embedding space can then be related to avatars of itself, as is the case with the partitioning of a vector space into different slices according to certain criteria²², or through dimensionality reduction, thus creating an equivalent space not from a mathematical point of view, but from the point of view of data description²³. But it can also be related to other spaces, as is the case, in particular, for translation functions that operate by establishing the equivalence of textual spaces of different languages; or for multimodality, which “aligns” spaces of sometimes very different natures, as is the case when a text prompt is used to generate an image (Figure 2).

These operations are often made possible by discrete metadata extrinsic to the space, allowing filtering according to certain criteria — that is, distinguishing and describing. But beyond their differences, the interpretative uses of embeddings are structured by a two-part approach: (1) a calculation internal to a navigable medium, and (2) the inscription of this medium within a larger network of objects of diverse natures. We can then see why and how an embedding space cannot be self-sufficient, however vast and

²¹ This middle ground was already noted by Nick Seaver: “Although they present the rigor of mathematical theorizing and algorithmic processing, they rarely meet the standards of mathematical proof or experimental verification. [...] They somewhat awkwardly bridge interpretative and positivist methodological tendencies.” (2021, 58)

²² For example, in diachronic studies where the dataset is “layered” into time windows and generates several embedding spaces that can then be related and compared using various metrics (e.g., Wevers and Koolen, 2020).

²³ Recall that after placing points in a high-dimensional space, it is common to reduce these dimensions using techniques such as t-SNE or UMAP. This offers the dual advantage of avoiding the “curse of dimensionality” (where the space is incomputable) and of making this unimaginable space visualisable. Thus, this vector space can become an image and join the long lineage of diagram-based scientific methods (Krämer and Ljungberg, 2016).

varied it may be. Indeed, the *word2vec* operational chain, which performs the transition from organic text to discrete tokens to continuous space, must itself be embedded in a network of other spaces. Different strata thus appear as so many conditions of possibility for a hermeneutics, among which is the continuously navigable embedding space.

Figure 2. Operational chain of *word2vec* (corpus — text — bag of words — latent space — network of spaces).

2. The theoretical structures of liquefaction

Beneath the promise of an “a-theoretical” fluidity offered by the fourth paradigm, the study of vector embeddings, such as that of *word2vec* or its modern competitors, shows that any “liquefaction” requires *structures* at various stages. The fluidity of data and navigation in a seamless space, dependent on the synthesis of a continuous medium, are therefore not only ensured by structuring operations, but are also embedded within a broader *media ecology* (subsection 1). A genealogy of diverse orders of knowledge then emerges, with which, far from making a clean break, the fourth paradigm maintains relationships of both rupture and continuity (subsection 2). From this perspective, it appears not only illusory to get rid of all theory, but, put another way, the computational operational chain is inhabited or worked by theoretical structures, often spontaneous (subsection 3), and which must be subjected to a “digital hermeneutics” in order to grasp their effects of meaning (subsection 4).

2.1. From the embedding to the latent space as a *medium*

From the corpus of documents to the bag of lemmas, to the embedding and its relation to other objects, it seems difficult to characterise the latent space as a representation. Indeed, we can say of it, with James E. Dobson, that it is “anisomorphic to the text” (Dobson, 2022) even though it *encodes* certain information relating to the corpus of documents and constructed from the relative frequency of occurrence of terms. Following Dobson, it is more relevant to leverage the concept of “mediality” to understand the place of latent space in this operational chain, and in particular that of re-mediation. Let us broadly define a *medium* as the material and symbolic site of a mediation between two alterities — a mediation which, through its materiality, shapes the relationship it creates and the emergence of meaning within it (e.g., Mersch, 2018).

We see that the latent space acts as a *medium* in a *chain of re-mediations*, that is, a material translation from one *medium* to another (Dumas Primbault, 2025a), during which certain qualities are gained — computability, visualisation (Krämer, 2022), scalability — while others are lost — contextual depth, text meaning, corpus organicity. From this perspective, the latent space appears as a form of mediation that

enables computation on entities linked by embedding, thus *within it* and continuously. The latent space is therefore a place in the sense of a finite and normalised space within which the subject of knowledge is immersed, mediated by other algorithmic devices such as clustering, dimensionality reduction, or visualisation tools. A space whose substance is the data itself and whose structure is the system of interdependence between the discrete units that presided over its synthesis and that lay, unstructured, in the bag of words. An “abstract and inert space, in other words absolutely controllable” (Dumas Primbault *et al.*, 2021) as a condition of possibility for a mechanical and deterministic computational practice.

Furthermore, “*medium*” is a polysemous term. While it designates the space in which meaningful units are inscribed and subjects navigate — here, a place rather than a *milieu* — it is also what is introduced between two alterities — a middle ground, a medium. Indeed, embedded in a broader network of other objects and thus lending itself to a series of operations involving equivalence, comparison, and relating to other spaces and datasets, the latent space appears as a *medium* inscribed within a *media ecology*. This ecology, however, is not continuous, resulting from the network-like relationship between tools and objects. The operational chain appears as a succession of *media*: from the corpus as a bag of words (a discrete set) to the vector space as a continuous space, to the ecology of tools as a network space.

A *medium* resulting from embedding textual data in a Euclidean vector space, the latent space is the dual condition for the navigation of the knowledge subject: firstly, within the space itself through computation, and secondly, between the space and other objects. Indeed, by inaugurating a continuous space for representing textual data and relating it to other spaces and other data, it enables and conditions the navigation of a mediated subject within this very space and between other spaces of mediation. Here we see the role played by the data infrastructure, in a metaphorical sense, which is to channel the flow of data by imposing initial and boundary conditions on the fluid flow, by prescribing an informational architecture to the medium.

2.2. From the continuity of space to liquid navigation

A place to navigate as much as a *medium embedded in a media network*, the latent space generated by *word2vec* highlights two major principles of the organisation of knowledge and its production throughout history (Foucault, 1969; see also Mackenzie, 2017, ch. 3). On the one hand, the structure of the spaces (physical or metaphorical) for the production, collection, and ordering of objects of knowledge, and on the other hand, the modalities of navigation (physical or mediated) of subjects of knowledge within these spaces. This is akin to the ancient library, with its ambition to possess all the world's knowledge according to an encyclopaedic and universal order, allowing for physical movement through its catalogs, shelves, and stacks — as well as controlling access to this knowledge. And if we follow the thread of the accompanying discourses relating to the recent evolution of this paradigmatic place of knowledge that is the library (Dumas Primbault, 2025b), it is possible to highlight to what extent the continuous space synthesised by *word2vec* is both in continuity and in rupture with previous orders of knowledge.

Indeed, the digital library, by providing more granular access to the documents it preserves and whose bindings it has “unbound” through digitisation, appears as a tool that facilitates the search for “information”, understood as a fragment considered factual. Thanks to hypertext, the online library amplifies the possibilities of navigating from one screen text to another, from one fragment to another within the browser, thanks to the “non-linearisation of the document.” It should be noted that this network-based structuring of the space for representing objects of knowledge is not specific to the online library but can be found in an earlier phase of the digital humanities that emphasised knowledge graphs and ontologies. Finally, the “data-driven” library would allow for the “breakdown” of silos

between collections, categories, and disciplines in order to open up a seamless navigation space, particularly for the benefit of algorithms capable of processing unstructured textual datasets²⁴.

The order of knowledge as prophesied by the fourth paradigm follows two trends noted here: firstly, the fragmentation of units of meaning (scroll — book — chapter — paragraph — data) into ever finer granularities, units which both constitute the space to be navigated and are represented within it; and secondly, the increasingly continuous, fluid, and liquid modalities of navigating this space²⁵. However, while navigation in the computational (hypertextual) paradigm was conceived as movement along links between discrete entities — as in a graph, an ontology, a controlled vocabulary, or a network — the fluid flow of the fourth paradigm relies on the synthesis of a continuous space from discrete entities²⁶. Thus, at the heart of the fourth paradigm, there is a homology between the fluidity of data and the frictionless navigation of the (mediated) subject within a continuous space. As is the case with the irruption of data into libraries (Mesguich, 2023), the datafication of text by *word2vec* inaugurates a continuous, *i.e.* “desiloed” space, ignoring the singularity of data, their diverse natures, their structures, in order to guarantee frictionless navigation within them.

Far from being natural or spontaneous, the homology between fluidity and navigation is made possible by the continuity of the space within which data and subjects move — Lury *et al.* (2012) speak of “ordering [culture] by means of continuity”²⁷. It is through a structuring operational chain (synthesis of a Euclidean vector space and its relation to other spaces) that, paradoxically, the breakdown of silos occurs. Indeed, the latent space generated by *word2vec*, while navigable without friction thanks to the mediation of analysis and visualisation algorithms, is fixed: the neighbourhood of a vector only changes on the condition of synthesising a new space from a new dataset, a new parameterisation, or a different embedding algorithm. Immersion as an instrument for creating continuity is a condition of possibility for frictionless navigation, at the price of the true liquidity of the data which are structured, crystallised.

2.3. The return of theory

Thus, the vector object is structured by a set of postulates that are rarely made explicit. What are these postulates? Let's mention a few. First, the text is considered as a sequence of words and not as a physical inscription in a particular *medium* (ink and paper, handwritten or typed, digital). This sequence of words is also tokenised in a strict and homogeneous way²⁸. Word order is irrelevant within the training micro-sets, and only the lemma is significant — disregarding any grammatical nuance. The space is static, generated once from a corpus, and a *word* will always have the same vector representation within it.

²⁴ Thus, historical places of production, structuring, and provision of data (Bermès, preface to Mesguich, 2023), libraries become, in light of the fourth paradigm, “databases” (Hey *et al.*, 2009, p. 27).

²⁵ Note that following this trend, the more continuous the space and the more fluid the data, the less the *embodied subject* moves, the more it is mediated by (digital) tools that move for it.

²⁶ While we stick to textual accompanying discourses here, there are nevertheless many videos that make use of *morphing*, or cross-fade, to show the fluid continuity between things (past and present, between images, etc.) and which is also found in multimodal models allowing visual journeys in latent space.

²⁷ As cited by Mackenzie (2017), who adds: “The phrase 'ordering of continuity' is interesting because we do not normally think of continuities as subject to ordering. In many ways, that which is continuous bears within its own ordering, its own immanent seriation or lamination.” (p. 65)

²⁸ As a symptom of this, the authors of *word2vec* are unable to use New York as an example of a city because its two words must be separated.

Although some of these postulates are no longer valid in today's major language models, which allow for the consideration of ever-increasing context, they nevertheless illustrate our point about implicit theory through *word2vec*, and the same exercise would apply to contemporary models²⁹. This critique is particularly necessary given that, for the past few years, we have been witnessing a shift within the digital humanities from a hypertext paradigm — that of the numerous TEI projects — to the genesis of a single vector space in which any object could be embedded³⁰. This eliminates the need for the manual clarification of these postulates, a process forced by graph and metadata encoding. While vectorisation does not invent the implicit structure of its data, it renders it invisible.

For behind these postulates lies an epistemology that, following Althusser (1974), could be described as “spontaneous” — that is, it seems to emanate directly from *praxis* without ever being problematised. Let us return to our example: *word2vec* has in its genealogy the structuralist presupposition that it is possible to capture part of the meaning of the text by reducing it to bags of words³¹. The vector space itself carries with it a set of cultural implicit assumptions: that language is continuous, as discussed above; that its space has several hundred dimensions; or that semantic proximity is a conceptual similarity — a culturally situated Western idea, as Seaver (2021, p. 48) reminds us.

Bearing this in mind, we can only agree with Andrew Goldstone and Ted Underwood on the necessity and the potential offered by variations in language models (2012). By playing on different stages of the operational chain — from data selection to training hyperparameters³² — to multiply the vectorisations of the same corpus, they demonstrate the renewed need for a more traditional textual hermeneutics, complementary to the digital kaleidoscope.

2.4. A digital hermeneutics

For among the prophecies of the fourth paradigm, the “end of theory” is also accompanied by the end of interpretation, the death of hermeneutics. Indeed, radical inductivism, rooted in an a-theoretical analysis of masses of objective data, is also the promise of an “automatic” production of immediate knowledge — that is, knowledge that is both instantaneous and unmediated. In particular, it is unmediated by human intelligence — which would in other circumstances be tasked with interpreting data, or the result of a calculation performed on that data —, because the data would speak for itself:

What often leads us to believe that the gap between manipulated calculations and interpreted signs can be bridged is the sophistication of the technical processes employed. Technical complexity would transform a difference in kind between meaning and calculation into a difference in degree: more efficient algorithms and larger datasets would then be the appropriate means to resolve this disconnect between meaning and calculation, interpretation and manipulation. (Bachimont, 2021, p. 8)

²⁹ This is something that their proprietary formats, for the most hegemonic ones, make impossible to investigate.

³⁰ The Impresso project (<https://impresso-project.ch/>) is an excellent example of this trend. It aims to bring together, in a single, comprehensive repository, data from press and radio archives preserved in text, audio, and sometimes visual form by more than twenty European institutions. Such a supposedly “seamless” space will allow users, for example, to navigate from a digitised and OCR-processed French newspaper clipping from the 1920s to a Luxembourgish radio broadcast from 1950.

³¹ In this sense, we could discuss Simon Lindgren's (2020) interpretation, which links *word2vec* — and its decidedly stable and static vectors — to the poststructural linguistics of Mouffe and Laclau.

³² Their work predates *word2vec*, and their vectorisations are obtained using LDA. But the idea would also be applicable to modern embeddings.

The order of knowledge announced by the fourth paradigm would no longer be descriptive and explanatory, but predictive and normative; the knowledge produced is evaluated by its effective action on reality. In immediate “adherence” (Rouvroy and Berns, 2010) with reality, knowledge would emerge from it without thesis, model, hypothesis or interpretation³³.

The return of theory in several places in the operational chain, which was supposed to be evacuated in order to ensure the fluidity of data and the frictionless navigation of subjects of knowledge, therefore also announces the return of hermeneutics too quickly dismissed by the diluvian prophets³⁴ — or rather highlights its irreducible presence, because “technical manipulation can only be an instrumentation allowing us to approximate the regime of meaning and not to induce it from textual or semiotic data” (Bachimont, 2021, p. 3).

Identified as a major characteristic of the epistemology of the humanities, the hermeneutic issue has been much debated in the field of digital humanities since the 2010s — sometimes reduced to a stark opposition between computation and interpretation, machine and human, or digital and analog (see, in particular, Gibbs and Owens, 2012; van Zundert, 2016; Drucker, 2017; Dobson, 2022; Krämer, 2022). What the *word2vec* operational chain shows is that in order to transform text into computable data and then synthesise a continuous space, it is necessary to interpret it according to schemas, theories, and models — that is, to engage in hermeneutics. While we cannot say that computation is a hermeneutic — “there is no text for a machine” (Bachimont, 2021, p. 10) — we can say that one or more hermeneutics are at work in the operational chain, whether practiced by humans or embodied by media — theories, models, formats — that are necessary for structuring data, designing algorithms, and visually organising results³⁵. That is to say, the operational chain of data processing necessarily mobilises something that is not already present in the data itself, as the end of the theory would have it. Computation and hermeneutics are indeed distinct but inseparable: while data analysis does not produce meaning without human interpretation, it nevertheless mobilises structures of meaning deposited in the machine by the subject:

The processes of selection, analysis, and visualization have their own hermeneutics. The dialogue on the hermeneutics of digital humanities cannot therefore simply oppose the quantitative and the qualitative, and relegate hermeneutics to a qualitative aspect of data interpretation, as if this data were not already value-laden and interpreted. (van Zundert, 2015, p. 335)

Ultimately, calculation is always already shaped by one or more hermeneutics and, in this sense, proceeds from the incalculable: computational manipulation is only made possible at the cost of successive

³³ Here we return to a recurring theme in the history of science: the “autograph” instrument which would allow nature to be inscribed immediately on a neutral support (cf. for example Daston and Galison, 2012).

³⁴ No terms from the semantic field of interpretation, meaning, sense, hermeneutics appear in Chris Anderson's article (2008), while Hey *et al.*'s work (2009) makes very sporadic use of them, e.g., “insensitive to individual interpretations” (p. 16) or “extract meaning from large and complex datasets” (p. 161).

³⁵ “The choices and methods involved in software design do shape the hermeneutics of digital humanities. Modeling encompasses the worldview of the model designer, her context, and her subjective decisions. Data models are anything but neutral — on the contrary, they are a purposefully specific selection of semantic categories and properties. Programming languages have paradigms that affect hermeneutics. Moreover, the reciprocal shaping of the hermeneutics of digital humanities by the methods of computer science extends beyond software design. The choices made in the analytical conception of any given digital humanities project affect its hermeneutic makeup. The choices of what properties to quantify, what probability distribution functions are chosen, which statistical tests are used, are in essence hermeneutically informed.” (van Zundert, 2016, pp. 343-344)

interpretive reductions. Thus, the object of this contribution, and of any reflexive practice in the digital humanities, becomes the development of a “digital hermeneutics” (Fickers *et al.*, 2022) in order to uncover the effects of meaning inscribed in operational chains despite the accompanying discourses of the fourth paradigm; that is to say, a critical reflection on what the digital does to research materials and to the epistemologies of the humanities and social sciences.

Conclusion: Towards an archipelago of epistemic communities

There is no data deluge here; by chasing theory out the door, it comes back through the window. Necessary for structuring data — from its format to its encoding, analysis, visualisation, and interrelation with other data — it is even a prerequisite for the continuity of a space that can then be navigated by a subject mediated by knowledge. The survival of theory at the heart of a fourth paradigm that would reject it is evidenced by the inextricable coexistence of paradigms sedimented throughout the history of knowledge. This epistemic diversity should be cultivated rather than a clean slate being advocated.

In fact, digital methods are not a replacement, but rather a supplement and addition to the arsenal of methods in the Humanities. [...] These procedures themselves are not performing hermeneutics; but at all stages, they are indispensably interwoven with human decisions and interpretations; they are complementary to the interpretative methods of the Humanities. (Krämer, 2023, p. 14)

And if we needed to find a new liquid metaphor to replace that of the flood and promote epistemic diversity, we could turn to Édouard Glissant’s “archipelago paradigm” (Glissant, 1990; Noudelmann *et al.*, 2020). The lake, rather than a formless mass, becomes the meeting point of multiple sources and the liquid expanse in the middle of which “islands of coherence” (Boullier and Ghitalla, 2004, p. 174) are sedimented, structured critically and reflexively through a “digital hermeneutics.” An archipelago that would draw its strength from the interconnectedness of the diversities that inhabit it.

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